

COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING IN ESL

Shahnozabegim Yokubjonova

Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign

Languages, young researcher

shahnozabegimyoqubjonova@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This research work informs the reader about the basics of communicative language teaching or communicative approach. Many people especially language learners are tired of old ways of studying and wants to have fun instead of studying with the boring grammar and sitting silent doing all the activities in a textbook. So, to share the better ways of learning and improve teaching process as well, I wanted to inform the learners about these practices. Below, through reading, the readers can find a lot of information here helpful for themselves.

Key words: learner-centered, innovative, independent, cognitive matter, grammar teaching, ancient methods;

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, to make learning more fun and easier, everyone is conscious of finding effective methods of teaching. As a young researcher, I also decided to try it. But of course, to my mind, there is no such thing as the best, simply, there are things that might suit one well. So, the method that most people find effective and helpful in their language learning process is Communicative Language Teaching. This method involves more communication and through this communication to improve for the better. Also, one more thing to make it stand out among other methods is that this method is learner-centered and thus, learners need to produce a lot of oral sounds and by doing so, they develop speaking abilities, which for sure helps other areas and qualities of the languages improve too.

MAIN PART

The methodology is full of different methods that have been in use for centuries. But as centuries pass, every method in the language shows both its powerful sides and faults clearly, especially, after being in practice for a long time. "The growing need for fluent communication skills in today's globalized world creates a challenge for foreign language teaching. Students must be given a proper foundation of communication skills that are demanded in different interactive real-world situations outside of the classroom. Students need to be prepared for real-life scenarios instead of just helping them to pass a superficial paper exam."

(Sanako, 2021) One of such methods, which is really powerful and showed its significance and role in the teaching world is a communicative language teaching method.

“Language teaching was originally considered a cognitive matter that mainly involved memorization. It was later thought instead to be socio-cognitive: language can be learned through the process of social interaction. Today, however, the dominant technique in teaching any language is communicative language teaching (CLT).” (Littlewood)

Some people see this method as an old method, like not a modern and innovative one. But also, for most individuals it's a young teaching method that just got into use a few centuries ago. It is so easy to judge methods by their appearance date and by the date in which that method was given an official name. However, I personally believe that almost every method in the world has been in use since periodical times of humanity. The reason why we do not have exact facts about it is because those methods were mostly used unconsciously and also, their popularity did not spend enough around the world to make them common international methods.

Learners in environments where communication is used to learn and practice the target language by interacting with one another and the instructor, studying “authentic texts” (texts written in the target language for purposes other than language learning), and using the language both in and out of class.

So, speaking of Communicative language teaching, it plays a big role in teaching, mainly in teaching a foreign language to the learners. Therefore, it is essential to understand this method and think of different ways of using this method in the classroom. First of all, let's look at this phrase and what it means. Communicative language teaching is CLT or it can also be called Communicative approach (CA) refers to interaction and communication between teacher and students in the lesson. “Learners converse about personal experiences with partners, and instructors teach topics outside of the realm of traditional grammar to promote language skills in all types of situations. That method also claims to encourage learners to incorporate their personal experiences into their language learning environment and to focus on the learning experience, in addition to the learning of the target language” (Nunan, 1991)

Literally, CLT is a little bit different from other methods and very unique. While other methods focus on the teacher and praise the teacher as a guide, in this method the teacher is just a facilitator.

Another unique feature of this method is that in this method, the most attention is given to oral skills rather than receptive skills. Teachers mostly conduct their

lessons not with grammar textbooks, but with simple interactions and reading books and articles.

“The communicative approach focuses on the use of language in everyday situations, or the functional aspects of language, and less on the formal structures. There must be a certain balance between the two. It gives priority to meanings and rules of use rather than to grammar and rules of structure. Such concentration on language behavior may result in negative consequences in the sense that important structures and rules would be left out.” (Mohammed Rhalmi, 2009)

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, I can say that to get the best results and to see the real effect of this method, one must use it in a classroom for sure, after that can say confidently that it really helped or not. We do really need effective methods for teaching and choosing this approach would certainly be a righteous way in this case. Above the basics about this method is mentioned and necessary comparisons are made.

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